

A quick draft essaying to contribute to the etymology of Rome, in Italy.

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- Roman mythology derived the name Rōma (Rome) from *Rōmulus*, name of the legendary founder and first king. This is almost certainly a [folk etymology](#), and the name of the mythical figure is more likely derived from the city name.
- Rōma may derive from **Roumon-* or **Roumen-*, an archaic name for the [Tiber](#) river that would be derived from the [Proto-Indo-European](#) root **srew-* (“to flow”) (for which compare [Ancient Greek](#) [ῥεῦμα](#) (*rheûma*, “river”) and [Στρῦμών](#) (*Strūmōn*, “Strymon, Struma”), [Albanian](#) *rrymë* (“stream”), [Lithuanian](#) *stràuma* (“stream”), and perhaps also Latin *rūmen*). If so, the intermediate source may have been an [Indo-European substrate](#).
- Rōma may be of [Etruscan](#) origin, as [PYM̃A](#) (*ruma*) was one of the Etruscan *gentes*, from [PYM̃](#) (*rum*, “teat”).

I have two potential contributions: the first is that Etruscan *rum* (said to mean “teat”, I have not yet verified that that is accurate) is itself from from the earlier meaning “to flow”. So it is likely that this “rum” was an Etruscan word of IE origin, or else a root in common between IE and Etruscan. If from IE, the root likely was **srew*, “to flow”.

In Thracian and Dacian, they had *Rome-/Roime-*, most likely meaning “strong”, and cognate with Old Greek/Ancient Greek [ῥώμη](#) = “**strength, might, power, force**”. Some reconstruct Thracian *Rome/Roime* back to an earlier **Ruma*. This *Rome/Roime* in Thracian is attested in the Thracian name *Roimetalkes/Rometalkes* (see also the variation in Dacian: *Boirebostes*, *Borebista*: as well as *Burebista*).

It’s interesting that the name of Rome in Greek is/was written [Ῥώμη](#), same as the word [ῥώμη](#), but the former properly written with a capital R. The word [ῥώμη](#) = “**strength, might, power, force**” is already thought to derive from [ῥώομαι](#) (*rhōōmai*, “to dash, rush”).

I have written in at least one other work of mine, I wrote how I posit that PIE **sreu-* also had the Pre-IE root meaning of “strength, force, might” included, not just to “to flow, stream”. One bridge between the two sets of meanings are the meanings “to rush, to flow strongly” etc.

So my second potential contribution is that *Roma* meant “strong”, not simply referencing the river, and *Romani* (Romans) likely meant “the strong (ones)”.

This is similar to my etymology which posits that *Daci/Davi/Dawi* meant “the strong ones/mighty ones” as well, but from a different IE root. See my work on the etymology of *Daci/Davi/Dawi*.